

Australian Research Data Commons

ARDC Data Retention

Partnership Call - Existing Collections

ARDC Storage and Compute

June 2020

Statement of Intent

“ARDC is a transformational, sector-wide initiative, working with sector, government, and industry partners to build a coherent national and collaborative research data commons. This will deliver a world-leading data advantage, facilitate innovation, foster collaboration and enhance research translation.”

The ARDC believes that to deliver a data advantage to Australian researchers and maximise the impact of research output of meritorious research, researchers must have timely access to high quality data collections. To assess the impact of data collections we will leverage research data management practices that enrich data collections with controlled and consistent metadata.

Project Purpose:

The Data Retention project is a 3-year (2020-2023) partnership model to support the retention of valuable Australian research data collections and to transition use of controlled international metadata standards that enable access, reuse and impact assessment of these collections. The project will drive an uplift in the description of data collections with 13 standard metadata elements. The ARDC will invite participation from all eligible organisations.

- Phase 1: A co-investment partnership will be invited from eligible organisations who manage existing research data collections stored on legacy RDSI capacity and having a minimal 'eligibility' metadata. Partners are required to enrich these collections to a more FAIR state (defined as having 'eligibility' and 'value' metadata) during the course of the project, 2020-2023.
- Phase 2: A co-investment partnership will be invited from other eligible organisations who manage valuable research data collections (defined as having the minimal eligibility metadata). Partners are required to enrich these collections to a more FAIR state (defined as having 'eligibility' and 'value' metadata) during the course of the project, 2021-2023
- Phase 3: Project closure will assess project effectiveness and build an impact and sustainability model to inform strategic vision and future investment targets.

From 2023 onwards, all ARDC partnerships seeking support for data collections will require those data collections to possess ALL 13 metadata elements.

ARDC will partner with eligible organisations to support underpinning capacity to maximise the impact of data collections from nationally meritorious research and secure them for future use in research. This project will build a definition of nationally significant data collections and by enriching them with best-practice metadata ensure they are more findable and accessible and reusable as part of a robust scholarly record.

Key Terms:

Term	Context for the purposes of the Data Retention Project
Eligible Organisations	Australian research organisations storing eligible research data collections, i.e. from nationally meritorious research according to NCRIS principles or national funding agencies. In addition, eligible organisations must be capable or have delegated authority to fulfil the assessment criteria (ARDC defined minimum metadata criteria).
Support	The ARDC will co-invest as partnerships to elevate existing national collections to a more FAIR state. The ARDC will welcome co-investment with matched cash contributions from each partnership for the duration of the project.
Underpinning capacity	The infrastructure and operational costs involved in storing and managing eligible data collections.

Nationally meritorious research	Research funded via competitive research funding programs, or undertaken through the principles and/or resources of the NCRIS programme.
Data collections	Data collections that arise from, or for use by, nationally meritorious research and are considered important to exist after initial project conclusion. All eligible data collections must be able to progress to their most FAIR state.
Future use	Use of data collections that occurs after primary purpose and not necessarily by the same researchers, sometimes referred to as secondary use.
Nationally significant data collections	A definition that will be built by the ARDC and partners to define what a nationally significant collection should be, how they may be identified and what benefits such designation can confer.
Findable	A data collection that can be found independently, i.e. by persons unconnected to the owner, primary project or custodian.
Accessible	A data collection that can be accessed independently, i.e. by persons unconnected to the owner, primary project or custodian.
Reuseable	A data collection that can be reused independently by persons unconnected to the owner, according to clear licensing conditions and minimal barriers.

What we will support:

The ARDC will co-invest in storage capacity burden to safely manage eligible data collections from eligible organisations, including Australian Universities and NCRIS capabilities.

How we will support:

The mechanism for support will be a 'base-rate' plus 'uplift' model where all partnerships are provided an equal, commencement investment, which is then supplemented by a second investment proportional to volume capacity of the data collections they maintain. The model is described below.

Benefits

Benefit to Research Organisations

This project will increase institutional compliance with R8 of the Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research.

“Provide access to facilities for the safe and secure storage and management of research data, records and primary materials and, where possible and appropriate, allow access and reference¹.”

Benefit to Infrastructure providers

ARDC will partner with infrastructure providers and research organisations in a transparent and equitable environment that attracts consistent ARDC support for both infrastructure and operations. This investment will underpin robust, reliable and high-quality data in a coherent national data commons. The international metadata standards used in this project facilitate data alignment and integration with other international initiatives such as the [European Open Science Cloud](#), [World Data System](#) and [DataOne](#).

Benefit to Researchers

Researchers will be able to more easily fulfil compliance requirements from major Australian (and international) funders for data management and the preservation of the evidence that underpins their research. They will also be able to draw from the growing body of data collections to fuel their future research with certainty and transparency.

This project will substantially increase a researcher's compliance with R22 of the Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research.

¹ Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research 2018. National Health and Medical Research Council, Australian Research Council and Universities Australia. Commonwealth of Australia, Canberra

“Retain clear, accurate, secure and complete records of all research including research data and primary materials. Where possible and appropriate, allow access and reference to these by interested parties¹.”

Benefit to ARDC

Supporting underpinning infrastructure and layering the FAIR principles on data collections will secure a significant and valuable foundation for a coherent national and collaborative research data commons. Lowering the barriers to find and access quality data collections enables data driven innovation, collaboration and research translation to maximise the impact of sector investment.

Researchers will routinely be able to find and have access to high-quality research data assets.

Application process

Applications for Phase 1 of the Data Retention project are invited from existing custodians of national collections supported by legacy RDSI investment.

Applicants will nominate data collections that can be registered in a public accessible metadata registry with 13 metadata elements

Applicants will submit a MS Excel spreadsheet nominating data collections along with six (6) metadata elements related to eligibility.

Applicants will also submit a financial budget detailing a proposed co-investment to this partnership according to the requirements of co-investment described below.

The ARDC will assess each submitted register of data collections against a recent audit of legacy RDSI records.

Over a period of consultation, up to the 21 Aug 2020, parties will agree the nominated data collections (recorded as a Deliverable 1 of contract) and terms and conditions in contract.

Once agreed, commencement may occur at any date from 10 July 2020 up to and including 24 Aug 2020.

During the course of the partnership the register of data collections will be enriched with a further 7 metadata criteria via the DataCite Metadata Registry, as described in the partnership model below.

Project Timeline:

Date	Item
30/4/2020	Distribute 'ARDC Criteria for Data Retention_20200429'
7/5/2020	NODES MEETING
29/5/2020	Distribute Partnership Model for comment
10/6/2020	Q&A1
17/6/2020	Q&A2
22/6/2020	Release Partnership Call (this call)
Upto 21/8/2020	Open partnership discussions begin
Upto 21/8/2020	Concurrent contract negotiations begin
10/7/2020	Earliest Notifications and commencement
24/8/2020	Latest Notifications and commencement
10/5/2021	Deadline for Review 1 submissions
31/5/2021	Review 1 result notification
10/5/2022	Deadline for Review 2 submissions
31/5/2022	Review 2 result notification
30/6/2023	Project Closes

Metadata Criteria - Existing Collections

Metadata used in the ARDC Data Retention Project will assess how nominated data collections support the FAIR data principles, in line with the ARDC strategic vision. This project will define, benchmark and track the effect of ARDC co-investment on eligible data collections stored by eligible institutions and work to provide a coherent national view of these data collections and their impact in the Australian research sector.

Ideal state

The ARDC will make use of contemporary and controlled metadata standards like DOI², ORCID³, ROR⁴ with minimal use of uncontrolled or free-text values (but recognise that some textual narrative remains a valuable source of contextual information). In addition to clearer assessment of investment impact, this project will significantly advance efforts to build a realistic and transparent sustainability model for support of high value research data collections that will define their content, where they can be found and how they can be accessed and reused.

Collections

For the purposes of the ARDC Data Retention Project, a “data collection” is defined as a logical structure of data generated as a significant output from, or input to, nationally meritorious research activity. Data collections may be the result of a single research undertaking, a national facility or NCRIS capability, or a collaborative effort within an international community. To realise potential, all data collections should be represented with the consistent minimal structural metadata so that they can be found, recognised, accessed, re-used and attributed.

The ARDC recognises that instantiation of this definition will be different across domains, disciplines and facilities. The goal is to apply a broad and minimal criteria which build a coherent definition of “data collections of national significance” whose wider research impact can be used, championed and supported for maximum impact.

Metadata Criteria

The ARDC Data Retention metadata criteria will be guided by the FAIR data principles.

To begin, the ARDC will support collections which are, or can be made more:

² Provided via the International [DataCite](#) Digital Object Identifier (DOI) service

³ Provided via the International [ORCID](#) service

⁴ Provided by the [Research Organisation Registry](#)

- Findable: Researchers, operating independently, are able to locate a metadata registry record of the data collection either via simple internet protocol searching tools, citations in traditional publications or other scholarly communications.
- Accessible: Researchers, operating independently, are able to access directly or with as few barriers as possible, the data collection which is described in the metadata registry record.
- Reuseable: Researchers, operating independently, are able to establish the conditions under which data reuse can occur and understand any obligations they must accept in reusing such data.

Collection assessment

In order to objectively evaluate collections in meeting this target, the following metadata are required. Metadata concepts are separated into two groups:

- eligibility metadata (the minimum requirement for application for support),
- value metadata (used to assess progress to a more FAIR state)

Each collection will be identified with a local ID and single copy capacity enumeration.

- For hierarchical collections, e.g. when multiple sub/or child collections exist as part of a higher 'parent' collection, applicants are able to nominate either parent OR child collections according to particular community convention for greatest reuse potential.
- For growing or versioned data collections, only 'versions of record' can be nominated, i.e. once they have reached a logical arrangement, are 'published' to a community and are immutable as records of research. For purposes of eligibility such collections can be accounted only once, with any additional growth being treated as an independent collection irrespective of whether it joins an existing collection.

Metadata related to Eligibility Criteria

This assessment determines the eligibility of the collection to be included in the partnership application.

Data collections will be selected by potential partners as eligible for support via this project. They must contain all of the following metadata to be considered in this partnership.

Metadata ID	Metadata Concept	Metadata concept type	Accepted value types
E01	Collection capacity	Single copy	Terabyte-TB (1TB = 10 ¹² bytes)
E02	Collection ID	ID at source/Local ID	User defined
E03	Applicable research disciplines	Fields of Research	Fields of research (FoR) codes. Can be 2, 4 or 6 character codes
E04	Title	A semantically relevant title of the collection	Free text
E05	Description	Abstract style description of the data collection	Free text
E06	Data Controller/s ⁵	Data controllers have responsibility for management of data and can apply licenses, access policies or other powers delegated from the data owner.	Research Organisation Registration (ROR) and/or ORCID.

⁵ Taken from the EU [GDPR](#) regulation framework for responsibility in data protection, in the absence of a clear definition of similar entity in the (Australian Privacy Principles) or from the Australian OAIC and Australian Privacy Act 1988. Data Publisher is often used to describe a Data Controller

Metadata related to Value Criteria

‘Value metadata’ are considered the minimum and achievable metadata required for data collections to be findable, accessible and reusable according to the FAIR data principles. Each partner will aim to increase criteria fulfilment over the contract period and the ARDC will conduct annual reviews to assess progress.

Metadata ID	Metadata Concept	Metadata concept type	Accepted value types
V01	Collection ID	Unique Persistent Identifier (UID or UPID)	DataCite Digital Object Identifier (DOI)
V02	Actionable Digital Registry entry	Landing page or registry entry that renders ALL metadata. Can be local data repository registry/repository or partners can make use of Research Data Australia ⁶	URL/URI
V03	Owner/s Contributors	Individual or organisational ownership declaration plus others involved	ORCID for individuals or ROR for institutions.
V04	Merit	Peer reviewed grant authority, or data citation or other metric that quantifies reuse and/or impact	Grant number Citation Other metric
V05	License	Open licensing framework and waiver notices	Creative Commons licenses and waiver notices
V06	Collection type	Collection characterisation	Conferring some understanding of the data collection’s characteristics, e.g. a dataset, image, model, workflow. Will be provided as a controlled list.
V07	Publication Year	The year collection was made available or if unavailable, the year it was registered in DataCite.	YYYY

⁶ <https://ardc.edu.au/services/research-data-australia/>

Metadata Registration

Once all metadata criteria have been fulfilled, collections will be registered in the metadata registry of the international data citation initiative, DataCite.

An xsd (current version 4.3) is publicly available for the DataCite MDR⁷ and this should be used to register via the DataCite Fabrica API according to your local service provider. ARDC maintains a subscription to the DataCite Fabrica service on behalf of its stakeholders.

A mapping of our metadata criteria to the DataCite Schema is provided below, the full schema tables with controlled values and definitions are provided in the project documentation. Additional schema elements are available for partners to use for even greater benefit, e.g. contributor, version, geolocation and format, but this will be left to the discretion of the partners.

Metadata ID	Metadata Concept	DataCite Schema ID	Comments
E01	Collection capacity	13 Size	Terabyte-TB (1TB = 10 ¹² bytes)
E02	Local Collection ID	11 AlternateIdentifier	User defined local ID
E03	Applicable research disciplines	6 Subject	Fields of research (FoR) codes. can be 2, 4 or 6 character codes
E04	Title	3 Title	Free text
E05	Description	17 Description	Free text
E06	Data Controller/s ⁸	4 Publisher	Research Organisation Registration (ROR). The role of 'Publisher' is given prominence in the data citation and will generally represent a primary role with rights over data collections or delegated authority from rights holders. Partners may wish to include the optional term 'contributor' (DataCite)

⁷ <https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.3/>

⁸ Taken from the EU [GDPR](#) regulation framework for responsibility in data protection, in the absence of a clear definition of similar entity in the (Australian Privacy Principles) or from the Australian OAIC and Australian Privacy Act 1988.

			schema ID) for other types of related roles, see V03 below.
V01	Collection ID	1 Identifier	DataCite Digital Object Identifier (DOI)
V02	Actionable Digital Location	12 RelatedIdentifier	Research Data Australia or other repository URL
V03	Owner/s (Contributors)	2 Creator (7 Contributor)	ORCID for individuals or ROR for institutions. Contributor is provided as an optional term that can be used for interests other than Publisher and Owner/s (which are mandatory) terms, e.g. a data repository or data storage service.
V04	Merit	19 FundingReference 12 RelatedIdentifier	Grant number (for 19) Citation IsCitedBy or IsSupplementTo or isReferencedby etc (for 12)
V05	License	16 Rights	ARDC recommends Creative Commons licenses and waiver notices. E.g CC0 where possible.
V06	Collection type	10 ResourceType	Controlled list values, most commonly dataset or data collection.
V07	Publication Year	5 Publication year	YYYY, generally taken to be when collection was made available or the year it was registered in DataCite.

Partnership Model

Commitment to Full Compliance

The goal of the Data Retention project is to enrich nominated data collections with thirteen (13) controlled metadata elements. As such, entering a partnership with the ARDC by accepting this model signals that the applicant commits to extending the seven (7) eligibility metadata criteria with a further six (6) 'value' metadata criteria over the duration of the project.

Period of Partnership

All partnerships will complete by 30 June 2023.

Investment Level

The ARDC Storage and Compute theme has an annual budget of \$6 million per annum for three years. It is anticipated that the Data Retention project will be allocated 50% of the total budget at \$3 million per year for three years (\$9 million in total). At its discretion, the ARDC Ltd Board may vary the theme or project allocation.

Co-investment

ARDC requires 1:1 matching co-investment for all infrastructure projects.

Co-investment must be in an auditable form (in accordance with reporting and accountability requirements as specified by the Commonwealth Department of Education) and can be cash (from project partners or other grants), investment from other NCRIS Projects, or effort/labour. NOTE: if contributing effort/labour, work on the project must be a significant amount of the person's time, i.e. 25% or more).

Investment Calculation

The ARDC has allocated \$5.4 million (60% of \$9 million) to this phase of the Data Retention project: support for existing collections. Subsequent phases will focus on supporting new collections and measuring impact.

The ARDC will distribute the allocated investment across all partners according to their share of the total reported capacity as assessed during the recent data collection audit. (see Graph 1).

Graph 1: Reported national collection capacity distribution across existing partners.

A total ARDC investment ' I_{ardc} ' for each partner will be composed of a base rate allocation ' b_1 ' (equal across all partners) and an 'uplift' allocation ' b_2 ' according to individual capacity share of reported collections (see Table 1). The ARDC investment will be matched with a 1:1 cash co-investment from each partner.

The total allocated investment for each partner will be a fixed financial cap:

$$I_{ardc} = b_1 + b_2$$

Node	% of TB	Base b_1 \$k	Uplift b_2 \$k	Maximum Total \$k
QCIF	0.20	309	648	957
Intersect	0.05	309	162	471
Pawsey	0.23	309	745	1054
TPAC	0.09	309	292	601
UoM	0.08	309	259	568
NCI	0.27	309	875	1184
Monash	0.08	309	259	568
Totals	1.00	2160	3240	5400

Table 1: Calculations based on a basic rate plus proportional share of capacity: 40% of the project allocation will be divided equally across all partners as the base rate. The remaining 60% of the project allocation will be divided as a proportional share of reported total capacity.

The derived unit TB cost for this investment is \$AUD65.5/TB (which excludes the base rate allocation).

Investment Distribution

The investment model distributes total investment across three reviews: 'commencement' and two 'annual reviews'.

A commencement investment ' b_1 ' will be payable following assessment against eligibility criteria and on successful contract execution. A review investment ' b_2 ' will be used to draw-down payments following two (2) annual reviews on 10 May 2021 and 2022.

Assessments

Commencement

To enter a partnership, data collections will be nominated by partners and assessed as eligible by possessing ALL 7 eligibility criteria and a commitment to enrich them further according to the 6 value criteria.

- **DELIVERABLE 1: List of nominated collections with all six (6) metadata related to eligibility criteria.**

On contract execution the allocation value 'b₁' will be available.

$$I_{contract} = b_1$$

- **MILESTONE 1: Commencement investment**

Annual Reviews

Over the contract term, partners will register data collections in a repository such as Research Data Australia (RDA) and the DataCite Metadata Registry (MDR). Annual reviews will require partners to submit to the ARDC a list of all data collection DOIs registered (or updated⁹) during the period. The review will extract metadata from the DataCite MDR and those collections that possess all 13 metadata criteria will be considered compliant.

- Only data collections with required metadata records in DataCite MDR and RDA or a similar repository will be considered compliant.
- Data collections with incomplete records in RDA or the DataCite MDR will be considered non-compliant resulting in a reduced investment for that period.
- Data collections that were incomplete in year 1 can be re-submitted as part of the 2nd annual review.

Annual Review 1

- **DELIVERABLE 2: Partners will submit a list of DataCite DOIs minted or updated for any of the collections nominated in deliverable 1 (or agreed exceptions, see below, 'Introducing New Collections').**

By the 10th May 2021, all partners will submit a report listing DOIs created or updated over the previous period. Review 1 will calculate a value variable (v_{r1}) as the capacity percentage of collections that are or have progressed to full compliance during year 1.

This value will be applied to the 'uplift' component 'b₂' and an investment reflecting progress assessment will be awarded: $I_{review1}$.

$$I_{review1} = v_{r1} \times b_2$$

⁹ If a DOI already exists for a particular collection then an update is acceptable.

➤ **MILESTONE 2: Review 1 investment**

Annual Review 2

- **DELIVERABLE 3: Partners will submit a list of DataCite DOIs minted or updated for any of the collections nominated in deliverable 1 (or agreed exceptions, see below ‘Introducing New Collections’).**

By the 10th May 2022, all partners will submit a report listing DOIs created or updated over the previous period. Review 2 will calculate a value variable (v_{r2}) as the capacity percentage of eligible collections (excluding collections previously designated compliant) that progress to full compliance during year 2.

Similarly, this value will be applied to the second contract value component ‘ b_2 ’ and an investment reflecting progress assessment will be awarded: $I_{review2}$.

$$I_{review2} = v_{r2} \times b_2$$

➤ **MILESTONE 3: Review 2 investment**

Note that in all partnerships $(v_{r1} + v_{r2}) \leq 1$

Introducing New Collections

New collections may be considered for inclusion into a partnership agreement after contract execution in two (2) circumstances:

- New collections can be ‘exchanged’ (per TB) for existing collections that are unable to meet targets.
- New collections can be ‘added’ (per TB) to existing sets of data collection during review cycles.

New collections will be considered at each review.

In all cases, new collections are treated as exceptions to the agreement and acceptance will require justification, be at the discretion of the ARDC and subject to available funds. All new collections are required to be 100% compliant with all metadata criteria.

Flow Diagram

Worked Examples

Example 1:

Applicant reports maintenance of 20% of the national collections.

A basic rate + proportional uplift will cap the ARDC investment at \$957k over the partnership period.

A commencement allocation ' b_1 ' of \$309k is awarded.

An uplift allocation ' b_2 ' of \$648k is retained for drawdown award following annual reviews.

During year 1, 50% of the nominated collections have been elevated to full compliance with all 13 metadata elements: \$324k is invested after Annual Review 1.

During year 2, the final 50% of the nominated collections are elevated to compliance with all 13 metadata elements. A further \$324k is invested after Annual Review 2.

Example 2:

Applicant reports maintenance of 9% of the national collections.

A basic rate + proportional uplift model will cap the investment at \$601k.

A commencement allocation ' b_1 ' of \$309k is awarded.

An uplift allocation ' b_2 ' of \$292k retained for drawdown award following annual reviews.

During year 1, 30% of the nominated collections have been elevated to full compliance with all 13 metadata elements: \$87.6k is invested after Annual Review 1.

During year 2, only a further 10% of the nominated collections are elevated to compliance with all 13 metadata elements. The final \$29.2k is invested after Annual Review 2.

Example 3:

Applicant reports maintenance of 27% of the national collections.

A basic rate + proportional uplift model will cap the investment at \$1184k.

A commencement allocation ' b_1 ' of \$309k is awarded.

An uplift allocation ' b_2 ' of \$875k retained for drawdown award following annual reviews.

During year 1, 50% of the nominated collections have been elevated to full compliance with all 13 metadata elements: \$437.5k is invested after Annual Review 1.

During year 2, only a further 30% of the nominated collections are elevated to compliance with all 13 metadata elements. During the course of the year a new collection set is identified that fulfils all metadata criteria and application is made to exchange 10% of original capacity for this new collection. The exception is agreed and the review allocates 40% as an outcome, therefore \$350k (262.5 + 87.5) is invested after Annual Review 2.

Disclaimers

The ARDC will not in any way be bound by the timeline indicated in this project documentation. It will be under no obligation to respond to or accept any applications in whole or in part including any pricing, costs or funding requirements specified in the applications, from any Applicant.

All information included in this partnership call is provided in good faith and believed to be reliable. Each Applicant must make its own enquiries about the information provided and shall be deemed to have satisfied itself as to the correctness and sufficiency of this partnership call.

Nothing in this partnership call requires ARDC to select an application and ARDC reserves the right to discontinue the application process (including any subsequent partnership call) at any time and for any reason.

By lodging an application, Applicants acknowledge and agree that:

- they will not make any public statement, or provide any information for publication in relation to the acceptance or otherwise of any RFP submission, without the prior written approval of ARDC;
- to the maximum extent permitted by law, neither the ARDC nor its employees, advisers or agents will in any way be liable to any person or entity for any cost, expense, loss, claim or damage arising out of or in connection with this partnership call;
- they have not relied on any express or implied warranty or representation made by or on behalf of the ARDC other than as expressly contained in this RFP or an addendum to this RFP;
- they have not received improper assistance from any staff member of the ARDC;
- ARDC may alter this partnership call, including its specifications / requirements, structure and timing, at any time and for any reason;
- ARDC may invite additional Applicants to submit an application at any time;
- they have not colluded with other organisations to inflate funding estimates;
- they understand that proposals will be treated as confidential by ARDC and that ARDC will not disclose application contents nor Applicant information, except:
 - as required by law;
 - for the purpose of investigations by the Australian Competition and Consumer Commission or other government authorities having relevant jurisdiction;
 - to the Department of Education and Training, at their request and if required, to enable transparency and accountability; and/or
 - general information from Applicants required to be disclosed by government policy and as part of the partnership approval process.

Appendix 1 - Draft Contract

<schedule 1 + Attachment 1>

Schedule 1	Activity Details
1.	Term of this Agreement
1.1	The Commencement Date for the Agreement is the date of signature of this Agreement.
1.2	The Agreement End Date is 30 JUNE 2023.
1.3	The Subcontractor is required to undertake the Activities and submit the Reports described in this Schedule 1 .
1.4	The Subcontractor agrees the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none">1.4.1 It will assure the accurate and complete representation of all nominated data collections with the metadata listed in Attachment 1 (herein referred to as ‘the requested metadata’),1.4.2 That by collecting and registering the requested metadata for all nominated data collections in the DataCite Metadata Registry according to the current MDR Schema¹⁰ it will follow good data citation practices in line with academic conventions of acknowledgement and attribution including responsibilities detailed in the ARC/NHMRC Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research,1.4.3 It will make reasonable efforts to ensure requested metadata for all nominated data collections are appropriate and persist for the duration of the agreement, according to DOI registration policy¹¹
1.5	The Subcontractor warrants the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none">1.5.1 It will faithfully represent rights of owners, publishers and other interested parties in accordance with the <i>Copyright ACT 1968</i> (Cth), or other relevant legislative obligations and,1.5.2 It possesses, or has delegated authority, or can direct an appropriate rights holder, to collect and/or present the requested metadata to be registered in a publicly accessible metadata registry.

¹⁰ <https://support.datacite.org/docs/datacite-metadata-schema-43>

¹¹ <https://support.datacite.org/docs/doi-registration-policy>

2. Activity

Project Title

ARDC Data Retention Project Phase 1: Existing Collections

Project Aims

The Data Retention project is a 3-year (2020-2023) partnership model to support the retention of valuable Australian research data collections and to transition use of controlled international metadata standards that enable access, reuse and impact assessment of these collections. The project will drive an uplift in the description of data collections with 13 standard metadata elements. The ARDC will invite participation from all eligible organisations. The first phase of this project concerns the ARDC responsibilities to existing legacy collections inherited from the RDSI and RDS initiatives.

Project Team

[Insert details of key personnel]

Milestones and Deliverables

Milestones/Deliverables	Planned activities to achieve the deliverables	Completion date
<i>Deliverable 1</i>	<i>Agreement on a list of nominated legacy data collections that are eligible to enter partnership by providing ALL six (6) eligibility metadata described in Attachment 1 clause 1.1.</i>	<i>[insert details]</i>
<i>Milestone 1</i>	<i>Commencement: Base Rate Investment available</i>	<i>[insert details]</i>
<i>Deliverable 2</i>	<i>Submit a list of new or updated DOIs for Review 1 of collections listed in Deliverable 1 registered or updated in the DataCite MDR with ALL metadata listed in Attachment 1 clauses 1.1 and 1.2. Assessment is made by ARDC for compliance against thirteen (13) metadata elements registered (or updated) in the DataCite Metadata Registry (MDR) during the period from Milestone 1 (commencement) to May 10 2021.</i> <i>Altering Deliverable 1 after milestone 1 is by exception and agreement only. Exchanging collections (per TB) or introducing new collections (per TB) remains at the discretion of the ARDC and dependent on available funds. All new collections are required to register all metadata listed in Attachment 1 in the DataCite MDR.</i>	<i>by 10/05/2021</i>
<i>Milestone 2</i>	<i>Proportional capacity calculation (V_{r1}) expressed as a ratio of capacity (TB) reported in Deliverable 1 and capacity (TB) compliance reported in Deliverable 2. Review 1 Investment available (V_{r1} proportion of ARDC Uplift Investment)</i>	<i>by 31/05/2021</i>
<i>Deliverable 3</i>	<i>Submit a list of new or updated DOIs for Review 2 of collections listed in Deliverable 1 registered or updated</i>	<i>by 10/05/2022</i>

	<p>in the DataCite MDR with ALL metadata listed in Attachment 1 clauses 1.1 and 1.2. Assessment is made by ARDC for compliance against thirteen (13) metadata elements registered (or updated) in the DataCite Metadata Registry (MDR) during the period from Milestone 1 (commencement) to May 10 2022 and which have not already been determined as compliant during Deliverable 2 Review.</p> <p>Altering Deliverable 1 after milestone 1 is by exception and agreement only. Exchanging collections (per TB) or introducing new collections (per TB) remains at the discretion of the ARDC and dependent on available funds. All new collections are required to register all metadata listed in Attachment 1 in the DataCite MDR.</p>	
Milestone 3	<p>Proportional capacity calculation (V_{r2}) calculated as a ratio of capacity (TB) reported in Deliverable 1 and capacity (TB) compliance reported in Deliverable 3. Review 2 Investment available (V_{r2} proportion of ARDC Uplift Investment)</p>	by 31/05/2022

3. Budget

Provide details of a high-level budget breakdown

Description of expenditure	ARDC investment \$	Co-investment \$	Total
Base Rate Investment	AUD 309,000	[insert details]	[insert details]
Uplift Investment (node specific)	Up to AUD xxx,000	[insert details]	[insert details]

Milestone/Deliverable	Due date	Invoice amount (ex GST)
Milestone 1 (Commencement)	[insert details]	AUD309,000
Milestone 2 (Review 1)	[insert details]	$V_{r1} * AUDxxx,000$
Milestone 3 (Review 2)	[insert details]	$V_{r2} * AUDxxx,000$

4. Reports

Report	Frequency	Content
Deliverable 1	Once	Full list of nominated data collections together with all six (6) metadata relating to eligibility as described in Attachment 1 clause 1.1
Deliverable 2	Once	List of DataCite DOIs of those collections from deliverable 1 that

		<i>have been registered or updated in the DataCite MDR with all 13 metadata elements as described in Attachment 1, clauses 1.1 and 1.2.</i>
<i>Deliverable 3</i>	<i>Once</i>	<i>List of DataCite DOIs of those remaining collections from deliverable 1 (i.e. not already compliant from Deliverable 2) that have been registered in the DataCite MDR with all 13 metadata elements as described in Attachment 1 clauses 1.1 and 1.2.</i>

Financial reports

Report	Details	Due date
Acquitted financial statement	Details of expenditure of ARDC funds and signed by the subcontractor's representative.	12 months from Commencement date
Acquitted financial statement	Details of expenditure of ARDC funds and signed by the subcontractor's representative.	24 months from Commencement date
Acquitted financial statement	Details of expenditure of ARDC funds and signed by the subcontractor's representative.	On completion

5. Party representatives and address for notices

5.1 For the purposes of this Agreement, the representative and address for notices of each Party is set out below.

ARDC's representative and address

[Name]	[insert details]
[Position]	[insert details]
Postal/physical address(es)	[insert details]
Business hours telephone	[insert details]
Mobile	[insert details]
E-mail	[insert details]
[Alternative contact]	[insert details]

Subcontractor's representative and address

[Name]	[insert details]
[Position]	[insert details]
Postal/physical address(es)	[insert details]
Business hours telephone	[insert details]
Mobile	[insert details]
E-mail	[insert details]
[Alternative contact]	[insert details]

5.2 The Parties' representatives will be responsible for liaison and the day-to-day management of the Funding, as well as accepting and issuing any written notices in relation to the Funding.

5.3 The Parties may, by reasonable notice to the other party, update the details of their respective representatives.

6. Other insurance required

Not applicable

7. Subcontractors

[insert details]

8. Additional work Health and Safety Requirements

Not applicable

Attachment 1. Metadata Relating to Criteria

1.1 Metadata relating to Eligibility Criteria

Metadata ID	Metadata Concept	DataCite Schema ID	Accepted value types	Comments/Guidance
E01	Collection capacity	13 Size	Terabyte-TB	ARDC requires volume capacity in terabytes (1TB = 10 ¹² bytes)
E02	Local Collection ID	11 Alternateldentifier	local ID	User defined local ID
E03	Applicable research disciplines	6 Subject	Fields of research (For) codes.	2, 4 or 6 character codes
E04	Title	3 Title	Free text	Brief title used to describe the data collection
E05	Description	17 Description	Free text	Contextual abstract description of the collection
E06	Data Controller/s	4 Publisher	Research Organisation Registration (ROR)	The role of 'Publisher' is given prominence in data citation and will generally represent a primary role with rights over data collections or delegated authority from rights holders. Partners may wish to include the optional term 'contributor' (DataCite schema ID7) for other types of related roles, see V03 below.

1.2 Metadata relating to Value Criteria

Metadata ID	Metadata Concept	DataCite Schema ID	Accepted value types	
V01	Collection ID	1 Identifier	Digital Object Identifier (DOI)	Specifically a DataCite DOI
V02	Actionable Digital Location	12 RelatedIdentifier	URL or URI to registry entry	Can be a local data repository registry or catalogue. Partners may wish to make use of Research Data Australia
V03	Owner/s (Contributors)	2 Creator (7 Contributor)	ORCID for individuals or ROR for institutions.	Creator roles identify rights holders and possess important legal status. Contributor is provided as an optional term that can be used for interests other than the mandatory terms of Publisher and Owner/s, e.g. a data repository or data storage service.
V04	Merit	19 FundingReference 12 RelatedIdentifier	Grant number (for 19) Citation 'isCitedBy' or isSupplementTo or isReferencedby etc (for 12)	
V05	License	16 Rights	Appropriate and formal licenses or waiver notices	ARDC recommends use of Creative Commons Licenses and waiver notices, e.g. CC0 where possible
V06	Collection type	10 ResourceType	Controlled list values	e.g. dataset
V07	Publication Year	5 Publication year	YYYY	generally taken to be when collection was made available or the year it was registered in DataCite.

Appendix 2

DataCite Metadata Schema + Guidance

DataCite

DataCite - International Data Citation

XSD is available via <https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.3/>

- 0-n = optional and repeatable
- 0-1 = optional, but not repeatable
- 1-n = required and repeatable
- 1 = required, but not repeatable

ARDC Data Retention ID	ARDC Data Retention Concept	DataCite ID	DataCite-Property	Occ	Definition	Allowed values, examples, other constraints	ARDC Data Retention Project Comments
V01	Collection ID	1	Identifier	1	The Identifier is a unique string that identifies a resource. For software, determine whether the identifier is for a specific version of a piece of software, (per the Force11 Software Citation Principles1), or for all versions.	DOI (Digital Object Identifier) registered by a DataCite member. Format should be "10.1234/foo"	
		1a	IdentifierType	1	The type of Identifier.	Controlled List Value: DOI	
V03	Owner/s	2	Creator	1-n	The main researchers involved in producing the data, or the authors of the publication, in priority order. To supply multiple creators, repeat this property.	May be a corporate/institutional or personal name. Note: DataCite Infrastructure supports up to 8000-10000 names. For name lists above that size, consider attribution via linking to the related metadata. Examples: Charpy, Antoine; Foo	
		2.1	creatorName	1	The full name of the creator.		

¹ Smith AM, Katz DS, Nlemeyer KE, FORCE11 Software Citation Working Group. (2016) Software citation principles. PeerJ Computer Science 2:e86 <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.86>

					Data Center Note: The personal name, format should be: family, given . Nonroman names may be transliterated according to the ALA-LC schemas2.	
2.1.a	nameType	0-1	The type of name	Controlled List Values: Organizational Personal		
2.2	givenName	0-1	The personal or first name of the creator.	Examples based on the 2.1 names: Antoine; Mae		
2.3	familyName	0-1	The surname or last name of the creator.	Examples based on the 2.1 names: Charpy; Jemison		
2.4	nameIdentifier	0-n	Uniquely identifies an individual or legal entity, according to various schemas.	The format is dependent upon schema.		
2.4.a	nameIdentifierScheme	1	The name of the name identifier schema.	If nameIdentifier is used, nameIdentifierScheme is mandatory. Examples: ORCID3, ISNI14, ROR4, GRID5.		
2.4.b	schemeURI	0-1	The URI of the name identifier schema.	Examples: http://www.isni.org/ https://orcid.org https://ror.org/ https://www.grid.ac/		
2.5	affiliation	0-n	The organizational or institutional affiliation of the creator.	Free text. The creator's nameType may be Organizational or Personal. In case of an organizational creator, e.g. a research group, you can add here the name of the formal institution to which the creator belongs.		
2.5.a	affiliationIdentifier	0-1	Uniquely identifies the organizational affiliation of the creator.	The format is dependent upon schema. Examples : https://ror.org/04aj4c181 grid.461819.3		
2.5.b	affiliationIdentifierScheme	1	The name of the affiliation identifier schema.	If affiliationIdentifier is used, affiliationIdentifierScheme is mandatory. Examples : ROR, GRID		
2.5.c	SchemeURI	1	The URI of the affiliation identifier schema	Examples : http://www.isni.org http://orcid.org https://ror.org/ https://www.grid.ac/		

² <http://www.loc.gov/catdir/cpsd/roman.html>

³ <https://orcid.org/>. When entering an ORCID, follow these style guidelines: <https://support.orcid.org/knowledgebase/articles/116780-structure-of-the-orcid-identifier> ¹⁴ <http://www.isni.org/>

⁴ <https://ror.org/>

⁵ <https://www.grid.ac/>

ED4	Title	3	Title	1-n	A name or title by which a resource is known. May be the title of a dataset or the name of a piece of software.	Free text.	
		3-a	titleType	0-1	The type of Title.	Controlled List Values: AlternativeTitle Subtitle TranslatedTitle Other	
EO6	Data Controller	4	Publisher	1	The name of the entity that holds, archives, publishes prints, distributes, releases, issues, or produces the resource. This property will be used to formulate the citation, so consider the prominence of the role. For software, use Publisher for the code repository. If there is an entity other than a code repository, that "holds, archives, publishes, prints, distributes, releases, issues, or produces" the code, use the property Contributor/contributorType/hostingInstitution for the code repository.	Examples: World Data Center for Climate (WDCC); Geoforschungszentrum Potsdam (GFZ); Geological Institute, University of Tokyo, GitHub	The Publisher is a primary role and used to generate data citation. To acknowledge related or enabling roles aligned to Publisher consider using 'Contributor' (7)
V07	Publication Year	5	PublicationYear	1	The year when the data was or will be made publicly available. In the case of resources such as software or dynamic data where there may be multiple releases in one year, include the Date/dateType/dateInformati on property and sub-properties to provide more information about the publication or release date details.	YYYY **** If an embargo period has been in effect, use the date when the embargo period ends. In the case of datasets, "publish" is understood to mean making the data available on a specific date to the community of researchers. If there is no standard publication year value, use the date that would be preferred from a citation perspective.	Has been included as a mandatory element for DataCite DOI minting
V06	Collection Type	10	ResourceType	1	A description of the resource.	The format is open, but the preferred format is a single term of some detail so that a pair can be formed with the sub-property. Text formats can be free-text OR terms from the CASRAI Publications resource type list.6 **** Examples:	For the Data Retention project this would be either a dataset or a data collection but partners are free to choose which ever 'type' value is useful. IT is included as a mandatory element for DataCite DOI minting

⁶ http://dictionary.casrai.org/Output_Types

						Dataset/Census Data, where 'Dataset' is resourceTypeGeneral value and 'Census Data' is resourceType value. Text/Conference Abstract, where 'Text' is resourceTypeGeneral value and 'Conference Abstract' is resourceType value aligned with CASRAI Publications term.	
		10.a	resourceTypeGeneral	1	The general type of a resource.	Controlled List Values: Audiovisual Collection DataPaper Dataset Event Image InteractiveResource Model PhysicalObject Service Software Sound Text Workflow Other See Appendix for definitions and examples	
E03	Discipline	6	Subject	0-n	Subject, keyword, classification code, or key phrase describing the resource.	Free text.	<i>For the Data Retention project, we will be using the 2, 4 or 6 FOR codes (AUSNZ Standard Research Classification 'Fields of Research Codes')</i>
		6.a	subjectScheme	0-1	The name of the subject scheme or classification code or authority if one is used.	Free text.	AUSNZ Standard Research Classification Scheme
		6.b	schemeURI	0-1	The URI of the subject identifier scheme.	https://www.abs.gov.au/AUSSTATS/abs@.nsf/Lookup/12970Main+Feature12008?OpenDocument	
		6.c	valueURI	0-1	The URI of the subject term.	Not required for the Data Retention Project	
(E06)	(Data Controller)	7	Contributor	0-n	The institution or person responsible for collecting, managing, distributing, or otherwise contributing to the development of the resource. To supply multiple contributors, repeat this property.	Note: DataCite infrastructure supports up to between 800010000 names. For name lists above that size, consider attribution via linking to the related metadata. Examples: Charpy, Antoine; Foo Data Center	<i>For the Data Retention Project the 'Contributor' element is optional but can be used to recognise an enabling facility of the Publisher, e.g. the name of a data repository within a University.</i>

					For software, if there is an alternate entity that "holds, archives, publishes, prints, distributes, releases, issues, or produces" the code, use the contributorType "hostingInstitution" for the code repository.	
	7.a	contributorType	1	The type of contributor of the resource.	If Contributor is used, then contributorType is mandatory. Controlled List Values: ContactPerson DataCollector DataCurator DataManager Distributor Editor HostingInstitution Producer ProjectLeader ProjectManager ProjectMember RegistrationAgency RegistrationAuthority RelatedPerson Researcher ResearchGroup RightsHolder Sponsor Supervisor WorkPackageLeader Other	
	7.1	contributorName	1	The full name of the contributor.	See Appendix for definitions. If Contributor is used, then contributorName is mandatory. Examples: Patel, Emily; ABC Foundation The personal name format may be: family, given. Non-roman names should be transliterated according to the ALA-LC schemas .	
	7.1.a	nameType	0-1	The type of name	Controlled List Values: Organizational	

					Personal (default)	
	7.2	givenName	0-1	The personal or first name of the contributor.	Examples based on the 7.2 names: Emily	
	7.3	familyName	0-1	The surname or last name of the contributor.	Examples based on the 7.2 names: Patel	
	7.4	nameIdentifier	0-n	Uniquely identifies an individual or legal entity, according to various schemes.	The format is dependent upon scheme.	
	7.4.a	nameIdentifierScheme	1	The name of the name identifier scheme.	If nameIdentifier is used, nameIdentifierScheme is mandatory. Examples: ORCID7, ISNI8, ROR9 , GRID10	
	7.4.b	schemeURI	0-1	The URI of the name identifier scheme.	Examples: http://www.isni.org/ http://orcid.org https://ror.org/ https://www.grid.ac/	
	7.56	affiliation	0-n	The organizational or institutional affiliation of the contributor.	Free text. The contributor's nameType may be Organizational or Personal. In case of an organizational contributor, e.g. a research group, you can add here the name of the	
					formal institution to which the contributor belongs.	
	7.5.a	affiliationIdentifier		Uniquely identifies the organizational affiliation of the contributor.	The format is dependent upon schema. Examples : https://ror.org/04aj4c181 grid:461819.3	
	7.5.b	affiliationIdentifierScheme	1	Name of the affiliation identifier schema.	If affiliationIdentifier is used, affiliationIdentifierScheme is mandatory. Examples : ROR, GRID	
	7.5.c	SchemeURI	0-1	URI of the affiliation identifier schema.	Examples : http://www.isni.org/ https://orcid.org/ https://ror.org/	

⁷ <https://orcid.org/> When entering an ORCID, follow these style guidelines: <https://orcid.org/content/journalarticle-display-guidelines>

⁸ <http://www.isni.org/>

⁹ <https://ror.org/>

¹⁰ <https://www.grid.ac/>

				domain of issue. May be used for local identifiers. AlternateIdentifier should be used for another identifier of the same instance (same location, same file).			
		11.a	alternateIdentifierType	1	The type of the AlternateIdentifier.	Free text. *** If alternateIdentifier is used, alternateIdentifierType is mandatory. For the above example, the alternateIdentifierType would be "A local accession number"	
V02 (V04)	RDA registry URL (Merit)	12	RelatedIdentifier	0-n	Identifiers of related resources. These must be globally unique identifiers.	Free text. For the Data Retention can be used to record RDA entry or data citation or other characteristic in the controlled list. *** Use this property to indicate subsets of properties, as appropriate. Note: DataCite Event Data13 collects all references to related resources based on the relatedIdentifier property.	<i>This element will record the RDA URL or other URL that registers the data collection Can be used to record citation of the collection as evidence of merit, e.g. in addition to or instead of a grant number, or to record versioning/obsolescence or other important characteristics.</i>
		12.a	relatedIdentifierType	1	The type of the RelatedIdentifier	If relatedIdentifier is used, relatedIdentifierType is mandatory. Controlled List Values: ARK arXiv bibcode DOI EAN13 EISSN Handle GSI ISSN ISBN ISSN ISTC LISSN LSID PMID PURL UPC	

¹³ <https://support.datacite.org/docs/eventdata-guide>

					URL URN w3id	
					See Appendix for full names and examples.	
12.b	relationType	1	Description of the relationship of the resource being registered (A) and the related resource (B).	<p>If RelatedIdentifier is used, relationType is mandatory.</p> <p>Controlled List Values:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> isCitedBy isCites isSupplementTo isSupplementedBy isContinuedBy Continues isDescribedBy Describes HasMetadata isMetadataFor HasVersion isVersionOf isNewVersionOf isPreviousVersionOf isPartOf HasPart isReferencedBy References isDocumentedBy Documents isCompiledBy Compiles isVariantFormOf isOriginalFormOf isIdenticalTo isReviewedBy Reviews isDerivedFrom isSourceOf isRequiredBy Requires isObsoletedBy Obsoletes 		

					See Appendix for definitions, examples and usage notes.	
		12.c	relatedMetadataScheme	0-1	The name of the scheme.	Use only with this relation pair: (HasMetadata/ IsMetadataFor) See Appendix for example.
		12.d	schemeURI	0-1	The URI of the relatedMetadataScheme.	Use only with this relation pair: (HasMetadata/ IsMetadataFor) See Appendix for example
		12.e	schemeType	0-1	The type of the relatedMetadataScheme, linked with the schemeURI.	Use only with this relation pair: (HasMetadata/ IsMetadataFor) Examples: XSD, DDT, Turtle
		12.f	resourceTypeGeneral	0-1	The general type of the related resource.	Use the controlled list values as stated in 10.1. See Appendix for definitions, examples and usage notes.
E01	Capacity	13	Size	0-n	Size (e.g. bytes, pages, inches, etc.) or duration (extent), e.g. hours, minutes, days, etc., of a resource.	Free text. *** Examples: "15 pages", "6 MB", "45 minutes"
		14	Format	0-n	Technical format of the resource.	Free text. *** Use file extension or MIME type where possible, e.g., PDF, XML, MPG or application/pdf, text/xml, video/mpeg.
		15	Version	0-1	The version number of the resource.	Suggested practice: track major_version, minor_version. Register a new identifier for a major version change. Individual stewards need to determine which are major vs. minor versions 14. Software engineering practice follows this approach of tracking changes and giving new version numbers. May be used in conjunction with properties 11 and 12 (AlternateIdentifier and RelatedIdentifier) to indicate various information updates.
						<i>Not required for the Data Retention project but can be used to register versioning.</i>

¹⁴ Based on the work of the Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP). For more guidance, see: http://wiki.esipfed.org/index.php/Interagency_Data_Stewardship/Citations/provider_guidelines#Note_on_Versioning_and_Locators

					May be used in conjunction with property 17 (Description) to indicate the nature and file/record range of version.		
V05	License	16	Rights	0-n	Any rights information for this resource. The property may be repeated to record complex rights characteristics.	The ARDC recommends the Creative Commons licenses and waivers but requires the authority of the rights owner/s	
					Free text. *** Provide a rights management statement for the resource or reference a service providing such information. Include embargo information if applicable. Use the complete title of a license and include version information if applicable. May be used for software licenses. Examples: Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Germany License Apache License, Version 2.015		
			rightsURI	0-1	The URI of the license.	Example: http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/de/deed.en	
			rightsIdentifier	0-1	A short, standardized version of the license name.	Example: CC-BY-3.0 Note: It's suggested to use the identifiers from the SPDX license list (https://spdx.org/licenses/).	
			rightsIdentifierScheme	0-1	The name of the scheme.	Example: SPDX	
			schemeURI	0-1	The URI of the rightsIdentifierScheme.	Example: https://spdx.org/licenses/	
E05	Description	17	Description	0-n	All additional information that does not fit in any of the other categories. May be used for technical information.	Free text. *** It is a best practice to supply a description.	
			descriptionType	1	The type of the Description.	If Description is used, descriptionType is mandatory. Controlled List Values: Abstract Methods SeriesInformation TableOfContents TechnicalInfo	

¹⁵ <http://www.apache.org/licenses/>

					Other	
					See Appendix for definitions.	
	18	Geolocation	0-n	Spatial region or named place where the data was gathered or about which the data is focused.	Repeat this property to indicate several different locations.	
	18.1	geolocationPoint	0-1	A point location in space.	A point contains a single longitude-latitude pair.	
	18.1.1	pointLongitude	1	Longitudinal dimension of point.	If geolocationPoint1Gis used, pointLongitude is mandatory. Longitude of the geographic point expressed in decimal degrees (positive east). Example: -67.302 Domain: -180 <= pointLongitude <= 180	
	18.1.2	pointLatitude	1	Latitudinal dimension of point.	If geolocationPoint27 is used, pointLatitude is mandatory. Latitude of the geographic point expressed in decimal degrees (positive north) Example: 31.233 Domain: -90 <= pointLatitude <= 90	
	18.2	geolocationBox	0-1	The spatial limits of a box.	A box is defined by two geographic points. Left low corner and right upper corner.	
					Each point is defined by its longitude and latitude.	
	18.2.1	westBoundLongitude	1	Western longitudinal dimension of box.	If geolocationBox27 is used westBoundLongitude is mandatory. Longitude of the geographic point expressed in decimal degrees (positive east). Domain: -180.00 ≤ westBoundLongitude ≤ 180.00	
	18.2.2	eastBoundLongitude	1	Eastern longitudinal dimension of box.	If geolocationBox27 is used eastBoundLongitude is mandatory. Longitude of the geographic point expressed in decimal degrees (positive east) Domain: -180.00 ≤ eastBoundLongitude ≤ 180.00	
	18.2.3	southBoundLatitude	1	Southern latitudinal dimension of box.	If geolocationBox27 is used southBoundLatitude is mandatory. Latitude of the geographic point expressed in decimal degrees (positive north).	

¹⁶ Use WGS 84 (World Geodetic System) coordinates. Use only decimal numbers for coordinates. Longitudes are -180 to 180 (0 is Greenwich, negative numbers are west, positive numbers are east), Latitudes are -90 to 90 (0 is the equator; negative numbers are south, positive numbers north).

					Domain: -90.00 ≤ southBoundingLatitude ≤ 90.00	
	18.2.4	northBoundLatitude	1	Northern latitudinal dimension of box.	If geolocationBox27 is used northBoundLatitude is mandatory. Latitude of the geographic point expressed in decimal degrees (positive north). Domain: -90.00 ≤ northBoundingLatitude ≤ 90.00	
	18.3	geolocationPlace	0-1	Description of a geographic location	Free text. Use to describe a geographic location.	
	18.4	geolocationPolygon	0-n	A drawn polygon area, defined by a set of points and lines connecting the points in a closed chain.	A polygon is delimited by geographic points. Each point is defined by a longitudeLatitude pair. The last point should be the same as the first point.	
	18.4.1	polygonPoint	4-n	A point location in a polygon.	If geolocationPolygon27 is used, polygonPoint must be used as well. There must be at least 4 non-aligned points to make a closed curve, with the last point described the same as the first point.	
	18.4.1	pointLongitude	1	Longitudinal dimension of point.	If polygonPoint is used pointLongitude is mandatory. Longitude of the geographic point expressed in decimal degrees (positive east). Domain: -180 ≤ pointLongitude ≤ 180	
	18.4.1	pointLatitude	1	Latitudinal dimension of point.	If polygonPoint is used pointLatitude is mandatory. Latitude of the geographic point expressed in decimal degrees (positive north). Domain: -90 ≤ pointLatitude ≤ 90	
	18.4.2	inPolygonPoint17	0-1	For any bound area that is larger than half the earth, define a (random) point inside.	inPolygonPoint is only necessary to indicate the "inside" of the polygon if the polygon is larger than half the earth. Otherwise the smallest of the two areas bounded by the polygon will be used.	
	18.4.2.1	pointLongitude	1	Longitudinal dimension of point.	If inPolygonPoint30 is used pointLongitude is mandatory. Longitude of the geographic point expressed in decimal degrees (positive east).	
	18.4.2.2	pointLatitude	1	Latitudinal dimension of point.	If inPolygonPoint is used, pointLatitude is mandatory. Latitude of the geographic point expressed in decimal degrees (positive north).	

¹⁷ A polygon that crosses the anti-meridian (i.e. the 180th meridian) can be represented by cutting it into two polygons such that neither crosses the anti-meridian.

V04	Merit	19	FundingReference	0-n	Information about financial support (funding) for the resource being registered.	It is a best practice to supply funding information when financial support has been received.	
		19.1	funderName	1	Name of the funding provider.	Example: Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation	
		19.2	funderIdentifier	0-1	Uniquely identifies a funding entity, according to various types.	Example: https://doi.org/10.13039/100000936	
		19.2.a	funderIdentifierType	0-1	The type of the funderIdentifier.	Controlled List Values: Crossref Funder ID18 GRID INSI ROR Other	
		19.2.b	SchemeURI	0-1	The URI of the funderIdentifier schema.	Examples: https://www.crossref.org/services/funder-registry/ https://ror.org/	
		19.3	awardNumber	0-1	The code assigned by the funder to a sponsored award (grant).	Example: GBMF3859.01	
		19.3.a	awardURI	0-1	The URI leading to a page provided by the funder for more information about the award (grant).	Example: https://www.moore.org/grants/list/GBMF3859.01	
		19.4	awardTitle	0-1	The human readable title or name of the award (grant).	Example: Socioenvironmental Monitoring of the Amazon Basin and Xingu	

Appendix 1: Controlled List Definitions

In Appendix 1, as in Sections 2.1 and 2.3 above, controlled list values that enhance the prospect that the resource's metadata will be found, cited and linked are indicated by shading. **contributorType**

Table 5: Description of contributorType

¹⁸ The Crossref service is called "Funder Registry" (<https://www.crossref.org/services/funder-registry/>) and Crossref Funder ID is the name for a Crossref Identifier.

Option	Description	Usage Notes
ContactPerson	Person with knowledge of how to access, troubleshoot, or otherwise field issues related to the resource	May also be "Point of Contact" in organisation that controls access to the resource, if that organisation is different from Publisher, Distributor, Data Manager
DataCollector	Person/Institution responsible for finding, gathering/collecting data under the guidelines of the author(s) or Principal Investigator (PI)	May also use when crediting survey conductors, interviewers, event or condition observers, person responsible for monitoring key instrument data.
DataCurator	Person tasked with reviewing, enhancing, cleaning, or standardizing metadata and the associated data submitted for storage, use, and maintenance within a data centre or repository	While the "DataManager" is concerned with digital maintenance, the DataCurator's role encompasses quality assurance focused on content and metadata. This includes checking whether the submitted dataset is complete, with all files and components as described by submitter, whether the metadata is standardized to appropriate systems and schema, whether specialized metadata is needed to add value and ensure access across disciplines, and determining how the metadata might map to search engines, database products, and automated feeds.
DataManager	Person (or organisation with a staff of data managers, such as a data centre) responsible for maintaining the finished resource.	The work done by this person or organisation ensures that the resource is periodically "refreshed" in terms of software/hardware support, is kept available or is protected from unauthorized access, is stored in accordance with industry standards, and is handled in accordance with the records management requirements applicable to it.
Distributor	Institution tasked with responsibility to generate/disseminate copies of the resource in either electronic or print form.	Works stored in more than one archive/repository may credit each as a distributor.
Editor	A person who oversees the details related to the publication format of the resource.	Note: if the Editor is to be credited in place of multiple creators, the Editor's name may be supplied as Creator, with "[Ed.]" appended to the name.
HostingInstitution	Typically, the organisation allowing the resource to be available on the internet through the provision of its hardware/software/operating support.	May also be used for an organisation that stores the data offline. Often a data centre (if that data centre is not the "publisher" of the resource.)
Producer	Typically a person or organisation responsible for the artistry and form of a media product.	In the data industry, this may be a company "producing" DVDs that package data for future dissemination by a distributor.
ProjectLeader	Person officially designated as head of project team or subproject team instrumental in the work necessary to development of the resource.	The Project Leader is not "removed" from the work that resulted in the resource; he or she remains intimately involved throughout the life of the particular project team.
ProjectManager	Person officially designated as manager of a project. Project may consist of one or many project teams and sub-teams.	The manager of a project normally has more administrative responsibility than actual work involvement.
ProjectMember	Person on the membership list of a designated project/project team.	This vocabulary may or may not indicate the quality, quantity, or substance of the person's involvement.
RegistrationAgency	Institution/organisation officially appointed by a Registration Authority to handle specific tasks within a defined area of responsibility.	DataCite is a Registration Agency for the International DOI Foundation (IDF). One of DataCite's tasks is to assign DOI prefixes to the allocating agents who then assign the full, specific character string to data clients, provide metadata back to the DataCite registry, etc.
RegistrationAuthority	A standards-setting body from which Registration Agencies obtain official recognition and guidance.	The IDF serves as the Registration Authority for the International Standards Organisation (ISO) in the area/domain of Digital Object Identifiers.
RelatedPerson	A person without a specifically defined role in the development of the resource, but who is someone the author wishes to recognize.	This person could be an author's intellectual mentor, a person providing intellectual leadership in the discipline or subject domain, etc.
Researcher	A person involved in analyzing data or the results of an experiment or formal study. May indicate an intern or assistant to one of the authors who helped with research but who was not so "key" as to be listed as an author.	Should be a person, not an institution. Note that a person involved in the gathering of data would fall under the contributorType "DataCollector." The researcher may find additional data online and correlate it to the data collected for the experiment or study, for example.
ResearchGroup	Typically refers to a group of individuals with a lab, department, or division; the group has a particular, defined focus of activity.	May operate at a narrower level of scope; may or may not hold less administrative responsibility than a project team.
RightsHolder	Person or institution owning or managing property rights, including intellectual property rights over the resource.	

Sponsor	Person or organisation that issued a contract or under the auspices of which a work has been written, printed, published, developed, etc.	Includes organisations that provide in-kind support, through donation, provision of people or a facility or instrumentation necessary for the development of the resource, etc.
Supervisor	Designated administrator over one or more groups/teams working to produce a resource or over one or more steps of a development process.	
WorkPackageLeader	A Work Package is a recognized data product, not all of which is included in publication. The package, instead, may include notes, discarded documents, etc. The Work Package Leader is responsible for ensuring the comprehensive contents, versioning, and availability of the Work Package during the development of the resource.	
Other	Any person or institution making a significant contribution to the development and/or maintenance of the resource, but whose contribution does not "fit" other controlled vocabulary for contributorType.	Could be a photographer, artist, or writer whose contribution helped to publicize the resource (as opposed to creating it), a reviewer of the resource, someone providing administrative services to the author (such as depositing updates into an online repository, analysing usage, etc.), or one of many other roles.

dateType

NOTE: To indicate a date range, follow the RKMIS-IS08601 standard for depicting date ranges.

For example:

<date dateType="created">2012-03-01/2012-03-05</date>

Table 6: Description of dateType

Option	Description	Usage Notes
Accepted	The date that the publisher accepted the resource into their system.	To indicate the start of an embargo period, use Submitted or Accepted, as appropriate.
Available	The date the resource is made publicly available. May be a range.	To indicate the end of an embargo period, use Available.
Copyrighted	The specific, documented date at which the resource receives a copyrighted status, if applicable.	
Collected	The date or date range in which the resource content was collected.	To indicate precise or particular timeframes in which research was conducted.
Created	The date the resource itself was put together; this could refer to a timeframe in ancient history, be a date range or a single date for a final component, e.g. the finalised file with all of the data.	Recommended for discovery.
Issued	The date that the resource is published or distributed e.g. to a data centre	
Submitted	The date the creator submits the resource to the publisher. This could be different from Accepted if the publisher then applies a selection process.	Recommended for discovery.
		To indicate the start of an embargo period, use Submitted or Accepted, as appropriate.
Updated	The date of the last update to the resource, when the resource is being added to. May be a range.	
Valid	The date or date range during which the dataset or resource is accurate.	
Withdrawn	The date the resource is removed.	It's good practice to indicate the reason for retraction or withdrawal in the descriptionType.

resourceTypeGeneral

Table 7: Description of resourceTypeGeneral

Option	Description ¹⁹	Examples and Usage Notes	Suggested Dublin Core Mapping
Audiovisual	A series of visual representations imparting an impression of motion when shown in succession. May or may not include sound.	May be used for films, video, etc. Example: https://data.datacite.org/application/vnd.datacite.datacite+xml/10.12608/ke-auckland_4620790.v1	MovingImage
Collection	An aggregation of resources, which may encompass collections of one resourceType as well as those of mixed types. A collection is described as a group, its parts may also be separately described.	A collection of samples, or various files making up a report. Example: https://data.datacite.org/application/vnd.datacite.datacite+xml/10.1594/paragea_877589	Collection
DataPaper	A factual and objective publication with a focused intent to identify and describe specific data, sets of data, or data collections to facilitate discoverability.	A data paper describes data provenance and methodologies used in the gathering, processing, organizing, and representing the data. Example: https://data.datacite.org/application/vnd.datacite.datacite+xml/10.17912/w2mw24	Text
Dataset	Data encoded in a defined structure.	Data file or files. Example: https://data.datacite.org/application/vnd.datacite.datacite+xml/10.1594/paragea_804876	Dataset
Event	A non-persistent, timebased occurrence.	Descriptive information and/or content that is the basis for discovery of the purpose, location, duration, and responsible agents associated with an event such as a webcast or convention. Example: https://data.datacite.org/application/vnd.datacite.datacite+xml/10.7269/03n35z	Event
Image	A visual representation other than text.	Digitised or born digital images, drawings or photographs. Example: https://data.datacite.org/application/vnd.datacite.datacite+xml/10.6083/n4n65c5	Image, StillImage
InteractiveResource	A resource requiring interaction from the user to be understood, executed, or experienced	Training modules, files that require use of a viewer (e.g., Flash), or query/response portals. Example: https://data.datacite.org/application/vnd.datacite.datacite+xml/10.7269/03n35z	InteractiveResource
Model	An abstract, conceptual, graphical, mathematical or visualization model that represents empirical objects, phenomena, or physical processes.	Modelled descriptions of for example, different aspects of languages or a molecular biology reaction chain. Example: https://data.datacite.org/application/vnd.datacite.datacite+xml/10.5285/d866cd2-c907-4ce2-b070084ca9779d62	N/A

¹⁹ Where there is direct correspondence with the Dublin Core Metadata, DataCite definitions have borrowed liberally from the DCMI definitions. See: <http://dublincore.org/documents/dcmi-terms/index.shtml>

Option	Description ²⁰	Examples and Usage Notes	Suggested Dublin Core Mapping
PhysicalObject	An inanimate, three-dimensional object or substance.	Artifacts, specimens. Example: https://data.datacite.org/application/vnd.datacite.datacite+xml/10.72299/X78052RB	PhysicalObject
Service	An organized system of apparatus, appliances, staff, etc., for supplying some function(s) required by end users.	Data management service, or longterm preservation service. Example: https://data.datacite.org/application/vnd.datacite.datacite+xml/10.21.938/3101ISNUCODNH1ZBQCVUVA	Service
Software	A computer program in source code (text) or compiled form. Use this type for all software components supporting scholarly research.	Software supporting scholarly research. Example: https://data.datacite.org/application/vnd.datacite.datacite+xml/10.4225/03/5954F738EE5AA	Software
Sound	A resource primarily intended to be heard.	Audio recording. Example: https://data.datacite.org/application/vnd.datacite.datacite+xml/10.72282/73167E05	Sound
Text	A resource consisting primarily of words for reading.	Grey literature, lab notes, accompanying materials, data management plan, conference poster. Example: https://data.datacite.org/application/vnd.datacite.datacite+xml/10.5682/9786065914018	Text
Workflow	A structured series of steps which can be executed to produce a final outcome, allowing users a means to specify and enact their work in a more reproducible manner.	Computational workflows involving sequential operations made on data by wrapped software and may be specified in a format belonging to a workflow management system, such as Taverna http://www.taverna.org.uk/ . More: ²⁰	N/A
Other	If selected, supply a value for ResourceType.		

²⁰ An education module on workflows prepared by DataONE is available at http://www.dataone.org/sites/all/documents/110_AnalysisWorkflows.pptx

relatedIdentifierType

Table 8: Description of relatedIdentifierType

Option	Full Name	Example
ARK	Archival Resource Key: URL designed to support long-term access to information objects. In general ARK syntax is of the form [brackets indicate optional elements]: [http://NMAA/ark:/NAAN/Name [Qualifier]]	<relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="ARK" relationType="isCitedBy">ark:/13030/tqb3k97gh8w</relatedIdentifier>
arXiv	arXiv Identifier: arXiv.org is a repository of preprints of scientific papers in the fields of mathematics, physics, astronomy, computer science, quantitative biology, statistics, and quantitative finance.	<relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="arXiv" relationType="isCitedBy">arXiv:0706.0001</relatedIdentifier>
bibcode	Astrophysics Data System bibliographic codes: a standardized 19 character Identifier according to the syntax http://www.ppppa.seehttp://infurlinfo/registv/QAHHandler?vefb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=reg&Identifier=info:ibibcode/	<relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="bibcode" relationType="isCitedBy">2014Wthr..69..72C</relatedIdentifier>
DOI	Digital Object Identifier: a character string used to uniquely identify an object. A DOI name is divided into two parts: a prefix and a suffix, separated by a slash.	Note: bibcodes can be resolved via http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/bibcode <relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI" relationType="isSupplementTo">10.1016/j.ejps.2011.11.037</relatedIdentifier>
EAN13	European Article Number, now renamed International Article Number, but retaining the original acronym, is a 13-digit barcoding standard which is a superset of the original 12-digit Universal Product Code (UPC) system.	<relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="EAN13" relationType="Cites">9783468111242</relatedIdentifier>
ISSN	Electronic International Standard Serial Number, ISSN used to identify periodicals in electronic form (eISSN or eISSN).	<relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="eISSN" relationType="Cites">1562-6865</relatedIdentifier>
Handle	A handle is an abstract reference to a resource.	<relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="Handle" relationType="References">10013/epic.10033</relatedIdentifier>
IGSN	International Geo Sample Number: a 9-digit alphanumeric code that uniquely identifies samples from our natural environment and related sampling features.	<relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="IGSN" relationType="References">IECUR0097</relatedIdentifier>
ISBN	International Standard Book Number: a unique numeric book identifier. There are 2 formats: a 10-digit ISBN format and a 13digit ISBN.	<relatedIdentifier><relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="ISBN" relationType="isPartOf">978-3-905673-82-1</relatedIdentifier>
ISSN	International Standard Serial Number: a unique 8-digit number used to identify a print or electronic periodical publication.	<relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="ISSN" relationType="isPartOf">0077-5606</relatedIdentifier>
ISTC	International Standard Text Code: a unique "number" assigned to a textual work. An ISTC consists of 16 numbers and/or letters.	<relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="ISTC" relationType="Cites">0A9 2002 1284A105 7</relatedIdentifier>

LISSN	The linking ISSN or ISSN-L enables collocation or linking among different media versions of a continuing resource.	<relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="LISSN" relationType="Cites">1188-1534</relatedIdentifier> <relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="SID" relationType="Cites"> urn:lsid:ubio.org:namebank:11815</relatedIdentifier> <relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="PMID" relationType="IsReferencedBy">12082125</relatedIdentifier> <relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="PURL" relationType="Cites"> http://publoc.org/foq/bar</relatedIdentifier>
LSID	Life Science Identifiers: a unique identifier for data in the Life Science domain. Format: urn:lsid:authority:namespace:identifier:revision	<relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="LISSN" relationType="Cites">1188-1534</relatedIdentifier> <relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="SID" relationType="Cites"> urn:lsid:ubio.org:namebank:11815</relatedIdentifier> <relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="PMID" relationType="IsReferencedBy">12082125</relatedIdentifier> <relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="PURL" relationType="Cites"> http://publoc.org/foq/bar</relatedIdentifier>
PMID	PubMed Identifier: a unique number assigned to each PubMed record.	<relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="PMID" relationType="IsReferencedBy">12082125</relatedIdentifier> <relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="PURL" relationType="Cites"> http://publoc.org/foq/bar</relatedIdentifier>
PURL	Persistent Uniform Resource Locator. A PURL has three parts: (1) a <i>protocol</i> , (2) a <i>resolver address</i> , and (3) a <i>name</i> .	<relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="PURL" relationType="Cites"> http://publoc.org/foq/bar</relatedIdentifier>
UPC	Universal Product Code is a barcode symbology used for tracking trade items in stores. Its most common form, the UPC-A, consists of 12 numerical digits.	<relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="UPC" relationType="Cites"> 123456789999</relatedIdentifier>
URL	Uniform Resource Locator, also known as web address, is a specific character string that constitutes a reference to a resource. The syntax is: schema://domain:port/path?query_string#fragment_id	<relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="URL" relationType="IsCitedBy">http://www.heatflow.und.edu/index2.html</relatedIdentifier>
URN	Uniform Resource Name; is a unique and persistent identifier of an electronic document. The syntax is: urn:<NID><NSS> The leading urn : sequence is case-insensitive; <NID> is the namespace identifier; <NSS> is the namespace-specific string.	<relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="URN" relationType="IsSupplementTo">urn:nbn:de:101:1201102033592</relatedIdentifier>
w3id	Permanent Identifier for Web applications. Mostly used to publish vocabularies and ontologies. The letters 'w3' stand for "World Wide Web".	<relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="w3id" relationType="IsCitedBy">https://w3id.org/games/spec/coIHCoil_Bomb_Die_Of_Age</relatedIdentifier>

relationType

Description of the relationship of the resource being registered (A) and the related resource (B).

Table 9: Description of relationType

Option	Definition	Example and Usage Notes
IsCitedBy	indicates that B includes A in a citation	Recommended for discovery. <pre><relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI" relationType="IsCited By">10.4232/10.ASEAS-5-2-1 </relatedIdentifier></pre>
Cites	indicates that A includes B in a citation	Recommended for discovery. <pre><relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="ISBN" relationType="Cites">07.61964312 </relatedIdentifier></pre>
ISSupplementTo	indicates that A is a supplement to B	Recommended for discovery. <pre><relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="URN" relationType="ISSupplementTo">urn:nbn:de:0168-ssoar.13172 </relatedIdentifier></pre>
ISSupplementedBy	indicates that B is a supplement to A	Recommended for discovery. <pre><relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="PMID" relationType="ISSupplementedBy">16911322/ </relatedIdentifier></pre>
IsContinuedBy	indicates A is continued by the work B	<pre><relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="URN" relationType="IsContinuedBy">urn:nbn:de:bsz:21-opus-4967 </relatedIdentifier></pre>
Continues	indicates A is a continuation of the work B	<pre><relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="URN" relationType="Continues">urn:nbn:de:bsz:21-opus-4966 </relatedIdentifier></pre>
Describes	indicates A describes B	<pre><relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI" relationType="Describes">10.6084/m9.figshare.c3288407</relatedIdentifier></pre>
IsDescribedBy	indicates A is described by B	<pre><relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI" relationType="IsDescribedBy">10.1038/data.2016.123</relatedIdentifier></pre>
HasMetadata	indicates resource A has additional metadata B	<pre><relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI" relationType="HasMetadata" relatedMetadataSchema="DHL" schemeURI="http://www.ddialliance.org/Specification/DDILifecycle/3.1/XMLSchema/instance.xsd">10.1234/567890</relatedIdentifier></pre>
IsMetadataFor	indicates additional metadata A for a resource B	<pre><relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI" relationType="IsMetadataFor" relatedMetadataSchema="DHL" schemeURI="http://www.ddialliance.org/Specification/DDILifecycle/3.1/XMLSchema/instance.xsd">10.1234/567891</relatedIdentifier></pre>
HasVersion	indicates A has a version (B)	The registered resource such as a software package or code repository has a versioned instance (indicates A has the instance B) e.g. it may be used to relate an un-versioned code repository to one of its specific software versions. <pre><relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI" relationType="HasVersion">10.5281/ZENODO.832053 </relatedIdentifier></pre>

ISVersionOf	indicates A is a version of B	The registered resource is an instance of a target resource (indicates that A is an instance of B) e.g. it may be used to relate a specific version of a software package to its software code repository. <relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI" relationType="ISVersionOf">10.5281/ZENODO.832054</relatedIdentifier>
ISNewVersionOf	indicates A is a new edition of B, where the new edition has been modified or updated	<relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI" relationType="ISNewVersionOf">10.5438/0005</relatedIdentifier>
ISPreviousVersionOf	indicates A is a previous edition of B	<relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI" relationType="ISPreviousVersionOf">10.5438/0007</relatedIdentifier>
ISPartOf	indicates A is a portion of B; may be used for elements of a series	Primarily this relation is applied to container-contained type relationships. Note: May be used for individual software modules; note that code repository-to-version relationships should be modeled using ISVersionOf and HasVersion Recommended for discovery. <relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI" relationType="ISPartOf">10.5281/zenodo.754312</relatedIdentifier>
HasPart	indicates A includes the part B	Primarily this relation is applied to container-contained type relationships. Note: May be used for individual software modules; note that code repository-to-version relationships should be modeled using ISVersionOf and HasVersion Recommended for discovery. <relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="URL" relationType="HasPart">https://zenodo.org/record/16564/files/dune-stuff-LSSC_15.zip</relatedIdentifier>
ISReferencedBy	indicates A is used as a source of information by B	<relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="URL" relationType="ISReferencedBy">http://www.testpubl.de</relatedIdentifier>
References	indicates B is used as a source of information for A	<relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="URN" relationType="References">urn:nbn:de:bsz:21-opus963/<relatedIdentifier>
ISDocumentedBy	indicates B is documentation about/ explaining A; e.g. points to software documentation	<relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="URL" relationType="ISDocumentedBy">http://nobilas-ilib.uniuebingen.de/volltexte/2000/96/</relatedIdentifier>
Documents	indicates A is documentation about B; e.g. points to software documentation	<relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI" relationType="Documents">10.1234/7836</relatedIdentifier>
ISCompiledBy	indicates B is used to compile or create A	<relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="URL" relationType="ISCompiledBy">http://nbn.info/gnd/4513749-3</relatedIdentifier> Note: may be used for software and text, as a compiler can be a computer program or a person.
Compiles	indicates B is the result of a compile or creation event using A	<relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="URN" relationType="Compiles">urn:nbn:de:bsz:21-opus-963</relatedIdentifier> Note: may be used for software and text, as a compiler can be a computer program or a person.
ISVariantFormOf	indicates A is a variant or different form of B	<relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI" relationType="ISVariantFormOf">10.1234/8675

		<p></relatedIdentifier></p> <p>Use for a different form of one thing. May be used for different software operating systems or compiler formats, for example.</p>
ISOOriginalFormOf	indicates A is the original form of B	<p><relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI" relationType="ISOOriginalFormOf">10.1234/9035</relatedIdentifier></p> <p>May be used for different software operating systems or compiler formats, for example.</p>
IsIdenticalTo	indicates that A is identical to B, for use when there is a need to register two separate instances of the same resource	<p><relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="URL" relationType="IsIdenticalTo">http://oac.cdlib.org/findaid/ark:/13030/c8178fq</relatedIdentifier></p> <p>IsIdenticalTo should be used for a resource that is the same as the registered resource but is saved on another location, maybe another institution.</p>
IsReviewedBy	indicates that A is reviewed by B	<p><relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI" relationType="IsReviewedBy">10.5256/F1000RSEFARCH4288.R4745</relatedIdentifier></p>
Reviews	indicates that A is a review of B	<p><relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI" relationType="Reviews">10.12688/f1000research.4001.1</relatedIdentifier></p>
IsDerivedFrom	indicates B is a source upon which A is based	<p><relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI" relationType="IsDerivedFrom">10.6078/M7D2067C</relatedIdentifier></p> <p>IsDerivedFrom should be used for a resource that is a derivative of an original resource. In this example, the dataset is derived from a larger dataset and data values have been manipulated from their original state.</p>
IsSourceOf	indicates A is a source upon which B is based	<p><relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="URL" relationType="IsSourceOf">http://opencontent.ku.dk/projects/81204AF8-127C-4686-E9B01202C3AD7959</relatedIdentifier></p> <p>IsSourceOf is the original resource from which a derivative resource was created. In this example, this is the original dataset without value manipulation, and the source of the derived dataset.</p>
IsRequiredBy	indicates A is required by B	<p><relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI" relationType="IsRequiredBy">10.1234/8675</relatedIdentifier></p> <p>Note: May be used to indicate software dependencies.</p>
Requires	indicates A requires B	<p><relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI" relationType="Requires">10.1234/8675</relatedIdentifier></p> <p>Note: May be used to indicate software dependencies.</p>

Obsoletes	Indicates A replaces B	<code><relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI" relationType="Obsoletes">10.5438/0007</relatedIdentifier></code>
IsObsoletedBy	Indicates A is replaced by B	<code><relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI" relationType="IsObsoletedBy">10.5438/0005</relatedIdentifier></code>

descriptionType

Table 10: Description of descriptionType

Option	Definition	Usage Notes
Abstract	A brief description of the resource and the context in which the resource was created.	Recommended for discovery. Use " " to indicate a line break for improved rendering of multiple paragraphs, but otherwise no html markup. Example: <code>https://data.datacite.org/application/vnd.datacite.datacite.e+xml/10.1594/PANGAEA.771774</code>
Methods	The methodology employed for the study or research.	Recommended for discovery. Example: <code>https://data.datacite.org/application/vnd.datacite.datacite.e+xml/10.6078/D1K01X</code>
SeriesInformation	Information about a repeating series, such as volume, issue, number.	For use with grey literature. If providing an ISSN, use property 12 (relatedIdentifier), relatedIdentifierType=ISSN. For dataset series, use property 12 (RelatedIdentifier) and describe the relationships with ISPartOf or HasPart. Example: <code>https://data.datacite.org/application/vnd.datacite.datacite.e+xml/10.4229/23RDEUPVSEC2008-5CO.8.3</code>
TableOfContents	A listing of the Table of Contents.	Use " " to indicate a line break for improved rendering of multiple paragraphs, but otherwise no html markup. Example: <code>https://data.datacite.org/application/vnd.datacite.datacite.e+xml/10.5678/LCRS/FOR816.CIT.1031</code>
TechnicalInfo	Detailed information that may be associated with design, implementation, operation, use, and/or maintenance of a process or system.	For software description, this may include the contents of a readme.txt, and necessary environmental information (hardware, operational software, applications/programs with version information, a human-readable synopsis of software purpose) that cannot be described using other properties (e.g. Language (software)). For other uses, this can include specific and detailed information as necessary and appropriate.
Other	Other description information that does not fit into an existing category.	Use for any other description type.

Appendix 3: Standard values for unknown information

Appendix 3 provides a set of standard values that may be used when mandatory property values are not available for various reasons.

Examples of usage:

```
<creatorName>:unkn</creatorName>
<title>:unas</title>
<publisher>:null</publisher>
```

Table 11: Standard values for unknown information

Code	Definition
:unac	temporarily inaccessible
:unal	unallowed, suppressed intentionally
:unap	not applicable, makes no sense
:unas	value unassigned (e.g., Untitled)
:unav	value unavailable, possibly unknown
:unkn	known to be unknown (e.g., Anonymous, Inconnue)
:none	never had a value, never will
:null	explicitly and meaningfully empty
:tba	to be assigned or announced later
:etial	too numerous to list (et alia)

Appendix 4: Version 4.1 Changes in support of software citation

Appendix 4 provides a quick reference guide for all the 4.1 version changes in support of software citation.

Documentation updates:

Property	Change to the documentation
Identifier	Add: "For software, a decision may need to be made about whether the ID is for a specific version of a piece of software (recommended by Force11 Software Citation Principles), <i>for a piece of software i.e. all versions or for the latest version.</i> "
Title	Add: "May be the title of a dataset or the name of a piece of software."
Publisher	Add: "For software, use Publisher for Code Repository, following the data model. If there is an alternate entity that "holds, archives, publishes, prints, distributes, releases, issues, or produces" the code, use the contributorType "hostinginstitution" for the code repository."
Contributor	Add: "For software, if there is an alternate entity that "holds, archives, publishes, prints, distributes, releases, issues, or produces" the code, use the contributorType "hostinginstitution" for the code repository."
PublicationYear	Add: "In the case of resources such as software where there may be multiple releases in one year, other DataCite metadata or information such as the landing page should enable users to identify the newest one."
resourceTypeGeneral	New definition for Service: "An organized system of apparatus, appliances, staff, etc., for supplying some function(s) required by end users." New example language for Service: "Data management service, or long-term preservation service."

	New definition for Software: "A computer program in source code (text) or compiled form. Use this type for all software components supporting scholarly research."
	New example language for Software: "Software supporting scholarly research."
relationType	Changes to Example and Usage Notes in the relationType Appendix: IsPartOf and HasPart: may be used for individual software modules; note that code repository-to-version relationships should be modeled using IsVersionOf and HasVersion IsDocumentedBy and Documents: e.g. points to software documentation IsVariantFormOf and IsOriginalFormOf: May be used for different software operating systems or compiler formats, for example.
Version	Add to Example: "Software engineering practice follows this approach of tracking changes and giving new version numbers." Add: "May be used for software licenses."
Rights	Add: "May be used for software licenses."
Description	Change definition of TechnicalInfo: "For software description, this may include a readme.txt, and necessary environmental information (hardware, operational software, applications/programs with version information, a human-readable synopsis of software purpose) that cannot be described using other properties (e.g. Language (software)). For other uses, this can include specific and detailed information as necessary and appropriate."

Appendix 5: FORCE11 Software Citation Principles²¹ Mapping

FORCE11 requirements	DataCite v 4.1	Comments
Unique Identifier – recommend a DOI	Identifier with IdentifierType 'DOI'	For software a decision may need to be made about whether the ID is for a specific version of a piece of software (recommended by Force11 Software Citation Principles), for a piece of software i.e. all versions or for the latest version.
Software name	Title	May be the title of a dataset or the name of a piece of software.
Author	Creator	May include those responsible for software creation.
Contributor	Contributor	For software, if there is an alternate entity that "holds, archives, publishes, prints, distributes, releases, issues, or produces the code, use the contributorType "HostingInstitution" for the code repository.
Contributor role	contributorType	See Definition in contributorType Appendix: Distributor: Includes distribution of software. See Example for

²¹ Smith AM, Katz DS, Niemeyer KE, FORCE11 Software Citation Working Group. (2016) Software citation principles. PeerJ Computer Science 2:e86 <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.cs.86>

		HostingInstitution: Includes software or run code repositories.
Version number	Version	See Version example: Software engineering practice follows this approach of tracking changes and giving new version numbers.
Release date	PublicationYear	See definition: In the case of resources such as software where there may be multiple releases in one year, other DataCite metadata or information such as the landing page should enable users to identify the newest one.
Location/repository	Publisher or Contributor/contributorType 'hostingInstitution'	For software, use Publisher for Code Repository, following the data model. If there is an alternate entity that "holds, archives, publishes, prints, distributes, releases, issues, or produces" the code, use the contributorType "hostingInstitution" for the code repository."
Indexed citations (and links between software versions)	relationType +	RelationTypes of use for software.
	HasVersion, ISVersionOf	HasVersion - The registered resource such as a software package or code repository has a versioned instance (indicates A has the instance B) e.g: it may be used to relate an unversioned code repository to one of its specific software versions.
		ISVersionOf - The registered resource is an instance of a target resource (indicates that A is an instance of B) e.g: it may be used to relate a specific version of a software package to its software code repository.
	ISNewVersionOf, ISPreviousVersionOf	ISNewVersionOf: can be used for "edition or software release etc." ISPreviousVersionOf: can be used for "edition or software release etc."
	ISDerivedFrom, ISSourceOf	ISDerivedFrom and ISSourceOf: Can be used to denote software that is a fork of other software or is the origin of a fork.
	ISPartOf, HasPart	ISPartOf and HasPart: may be used for individual software modules
	ISDocumentedBy, Documents	ISDocumentedBy and Documents: e.g. points to software documentation
	ISVariantFormOf, ISOriginalFormOf	ISVariantFormOf and ISOriginalFormOf: May be used for different software operating systems or compiler formats, for example. Indicates
		that A is a variant or different form or packaging of B.

	IsRequiredBy, Requires	IsRequiredBy: the registered resource A is called by or is required by software resource B. Requires: the registered resource A calls or requires software resource B. See example: May be used for software licenses.
Software licenses	Rights	
Description	Description	TechnicalInfo: for software description, this may include a readme text, and necessary environmental information (hardware, operational software, applications/programs) that cannot be described using other properties such as 'Format/version' or 'Description/summary'
	Description with descriptionType 'TechnicalInfo' descriptionType 'Abstra'	
	Description with descriptionType 'Abstra'	
Keywords	Subject	Existing guidance applies: Subject, keyword, classification code, or key phrase describing the resource.